

Limenitis a. arthemis (White Admiral) in coastal southeastern Virginia.

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ABSTRACT. *Limenitis a. arthemis* is reported from coastal southeastern Virginia for the first time.

Additional key words: Kiptopeke, Northampton County, Jamestown, James City County.

INTRODUCTION

Limenitis a. arthemis (White Admiral) resides in boreal and transition zone forests of Canada and northern United States (Cech & Tudor, 2005). It rarely occurs within the range of southern subspecies, *L. a. astyanax* (Red-spotted Purple). Prior to 2019, only eight records of the White Admiral were known from Virginia: Albemarle, Bath, Fluvanna, Frederick, Henrico, Nelson, Rockingham Counties, and Charlottesville City. Clark & Clark (1951), Pl. 6g, illustrate an odd intergrade with white *arthemis* bands on the forewings only.

OBSERVATIONS

On 27 Jul 2019, a White Admiral butterfly was spotted by staff at Kiptopeke SP, Northampton County, VA. The reporting individual was also a seasonal biologist at the Coastal Virginia Wildlife Observatory. No photo was obtained, but the reporting individual was familiar with the species from living in Massachusetts. The following day, the Observatory conducted its annual NABA 4th of July Butterfly Count in the area and searched unsuccessfully for the butterfly. The habitat at Kiptopeke is a *Pinus taeda* (Coastal Plain Loblolly Pine) and *Quercus* sp. (Oak) forest with an understory of *Ilex opaca* (American Holly), *Prunus serotina* (Black Cherry), *Celtis occidentalis* (Hackberry), and *Toxicodendron radicans* (Poison Ivy). *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrods) are the primary nectar sources.

On 6 Aug 2019, the Observatory's Pearly-eye Survey Team found and photographed a White Admiral near Jamestown in James City County, VA. (**Fig. 1**). This discovery occurred across the Chesapeake Bay approximately 30 miles from the Kiptopeke observation. The Jamestown habitat is similar and consists of a Coastal Plain Loblolly Pine & Oak forest, with an understory of American Holly, *Arundinaria tecta* (Switch Cane) and the invasive *Microstegium vimineum* (Japanese Stiltgrass).

I am not aware of other records of White Admirals in coastal Virginia.

Fig. 1. White Admiral, Jamestown, VA, 6 Aug 2019.

REFERENCES

- Cech, R. & G. Tudor. 2005. Butterflies of the East Coast, an Observer's Guide. Princeton University Press, Princeton, N.J. xii + 345 pp.
- Clark, A. H. & L. F. Clark. 1951. The Butterflies of Virginia. Smithsonian Miscellaneous Collections 116(7): 1-239.